

ECOLOGICAL REQUIREMENTS, OBJECTIVES, AND GOALS OF ECOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF ENERGY-ACTIVE BUILDINGS

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The energy system of a building is a specific engineering system designed to ensure the required operating conditions for facilities. As is well known, an energy system can be used for heating and cooling a building, as well as for powering the devices and installations located within it. The conditions and objectives of a building's construction define the set of requirements for its energy system. Ecological requirements are implemented both directly during the creation of the energy system and indirectly by establishing the conditions for its operation.

The problem of building energy supply can be addressed either solely within the scope of an individual building or a concentrated group of buildings in a specific area, or as part of a broader energy, environmental, or social program. The second approach appears to be more effective. It is essential to emphasize that the ecological assessment of the building energy supply issue should not be carried out for each individual project but rather for the entire sector. This should cover a territorial scale such as a region, a natural zone, or another designated area.

The ecological consequences of using various energy systems in buildings must be analyzed considering the range of phenomena observed during the production, transmission, and utilization of energy within the building. These phenomena are primarily determined by the type of energy system employed.

The integration of ecological principles in engineering design and the ecological requirements for engineering systems constitute the core of sustainable design practices. The primary goal of this process is environmental protection. [1.3]

Relevance of Environmental Topics and the Emergence of New Scientific Fields. The growing focus on environmental issues has led to the emergence of new scientific disciplines, including urban ecology. Some authors use the incorrect term "urban planning ecology"; however, ecology is a unified and indivisible science with different aspects depending on the research area. Highlighting the city as a unique object within the environment allows ecology to study one of the most critical components of the technosphere [12]. Urban ecology is a scientific discipline that examines the interactions between urban societies and the surrounding environment. The development of this field is a result of the increasing environmental focus of science.

Based on an analysis of the modern experience in constructing and operating energy-active buildings, a system of ecological indicators has been developed to

guide project decisions and assess designs for such buildings. These indicators are universal and independent of the technical features of the energy system, the construction site, or the type of energy source used [11].

Construction Site Conditions. Site conditions significantly influence the economic efficiency of the energy system. For instance, the shortest path for a heat carrier is chosen if energy transfer from a stationary source (e.g., a geothermal well) is required. For other energy sources, factors like microclimate, topography, vegetation, and geological conditions of the site play a role. The size of the allocated area also affects the organization of construction work [10].

The orientation of a building generally impacts its thermal performance. For systems with solar installations, the building's orientation is selected to optimize solar gain, while for wind energy systems, towers with wind turbines are positioned accordingly [14].

Energy System Selection. The choice of an energy system depends on specific construction conditions, energy demand, and local energy sources. The same energy system can be implemented differently depending on building layout and other factors. Typically, multiple options are available for designing energy systems [9].

The main condition for the efficient operation of an energy system is aligning the energy output with the building's needs in the most cost-effective manner. In cases where multiple energy sources are available, planning may focus on optimizing the system's operation to meet energy demands most favorably. For instance, during specific times of the day, it may be necessary to stabilize energy supply parameters for equipment by connecting consumers to an energy storage system, which may perform better than a wind turbine under certain conditions [13].

Despite the relative environmental safety of many unconventional energy sources, their potential impacts must still be evaluated [8]. This is particularly true for systems using geothermal energy.

Environmental Considerations in Design. The discussed set of indicators is taken into account alongside economic and operational characteristics during project design. Building energy supply is one of the applied engineering tasks in construction. Recently, this task has begun to incorporate data from natural sciences, focusing on forecasting ecological conditions on a scale larger than an individual building or city. This is due to two reasons:

1. The finite nature of energy resources requires solutions that address not only the spatial and structural organization of living environments but also the methods of obtaining energy for building operation [7].

2. The growing energy consumption of humanity intensifies the anthropogenic impact on the environment, sometimes leading to negative environmental changes.

Integration of Ecology and Technology. Modern science is characterized by the differentiation of scientific disciplines and increased specialization. While the separation of ecology from technical sciences initially seemed reasonable due to minimal human impact on the biosphere, the rapid growth of the technosphere has changed this dynamic. Human activity has become a "powerful geological force," necessitating the management of anthropogenic activities to maintain favorable conditions for current and future generations [6]. This has led to the integration of ecological principles into technical sciences and systemic approaches to ecological management.

The Relationship Between the Biosphere and Technosphere. The biosphere consists of living and non-living matter. Human activity has created the technosphere, a part of the non-living environment designed to meet humanity's needs. The relationship between the biosphere and the technosphere reflects the dynamic between nature and society. The technosphere's development must minimize its negative impact on the biosphere by ensuring an ecological balance.

To achieve this, interdisciplinary collaboration is required. Fundamental research on the biosphere conducted at academic and interdepartmental levels must connect with applied research carried out by individual sectors [5].

Construction as a Driver of Technosphere Development. Construction is one of the most active sectors shaping the technosphere, with settlement patterns as a key indicator of its expansion and complexity. Therefore, the primary ecological principle of technosphere development is particularly relevant to construction.

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